

Cytotoxic activity of methanolic leaf extract of *Drypetes sepiaria* with caspase-3 activation potential in human cervical cancer (HeLa) cell line

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Abstract : From past few decades, medicinal plants have been reported as conventional anti-cancer agents. The aim of the present work was to investigate the cytotoxic activity of *Drypetes sepiaria*. In the present study, the methanolic extracts of leaves were screened for its cytotoxic activity against human cervical carcinoma cell (HeLa) by using MTT assay. A further, to provide evidence for involvement of apoptosis, the caspase-3 activated cells were quantified flow cytometrically by fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS). The extract was more toxic to HeLa cell line with IC50 value of 10 µg/mL respectively. Further, treatment of 10 µg/mL methanolic extract at 12 h was shown to increase caspase-3 cells from 0.24% to 60%, indicating that the observed cytotoxicity was mediated via apoptosis. The bio active components which may responsible for the cytotoxicity of methanolic extracts were further separated and analyzed by GC-MS.

Keywords : Apoptosis, cytotoxicity, Euphorbiaceae, *D. sepiaria*.

Introduction

Over a past few decades, cancer has become a major cause of death and it is kept on increasing year by year. Cervical cancer caused due to human Papilloma Virus (HPV) is the most frequent malignity in Indian women, which is responsible for substantial morbidity and death rate in woman worldwide¹. Traditional medicines act as a source of easily available effective anticancer agent to people with a broad spectrum of action like high percentage of cure with single therapeutic dose, cost effective and free from toxicity. Hence, a major research is devoted to develop anticancer agents from plants.

The genus *Drypetes* is comprised of approximately 160 species which has been used in the folk medicine². These plants are extensively used in African folk medicine to treat various diseases³. It is worth noting that the species was different, although these genus have been used to treat similar disorders. The plants of this genus are reported to have flavonoids, chalcone glycosides, saponins, tripterpenoids, phenolics, alkaloids etc.⁴.

Drypetes sepiaria (*D. sepiaria*) belongs to the family Euphorbiaceae. It is locally known as Kalvirai (Tamil).

This plant is used in folk medicine by tribal people of the Western Ghats to treat pain and inflammation. The seeds of this plant are used as a wild edible food by Palliyars⁵, India. The decoction of leaves and seeds of this plant is also given for reducing rheumatic inflammation⁶. As per our literature reports, till date there is no scientific investigations found on species *D. sepiaria* on both of its pharmacological properties as well as phyto constituents present. In the present study to the best of our knowledge, we aimed for the first time to investigate cytotoxic effects of methanolic extracts of leaves of *D. sepiaria* on cervical cancer cells HeLa. Furthermore, we evaluated the induction of apoptosis.

Materials and methods :

Preparation of extracts :

Fresh leaves of *D. sepiaria* were collected from Puducherry (Coordinates : 11°58'5"N, 79°48'42"E), India, during the month of January, 2011. The leaves were identified and authenticated by using various taxonomic markers and other available literature by consulting a botanist in Voorhees College, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India. The extracts were prepared according to our previous reports¹⁵.

Cell culture :

The HeLa cells were assumed from National Centre for Cell Sciences, Pune, India. The cells were grown in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (HIMEDIA Labs Pvt. Ltd.) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (HIMEDIA Labs Pvt. Ltd.) in the presence of 100 units/ml of penicillin and 0.1 mg/ml of streptomycin and the cells were incubated in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂ in the incubator.

Cytotoxicity assay by MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay method :

The cytotoxicity effects of methanolic extracts of leaf against HeLa cell lines were determined by the MTT dye uptake method. The HeLa cells (6×10^5 cells/ml) seeded and cultured in 96-well microtitre plate for 24 h. Further, the cells were treated with varying concentrations (0.01, 0.1, 1, 10 and 100 µg/ml) of a methanolic leaf extract of *D. sepiaria* for 24 h at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator. Afterwards the photographs of the cells were taken by observing under an inverted phase contrast microscope (Labomed, Germany). Thenceforth 25 µL of MTT (Sigma, St. Louis, MO) solution (5 mg/ml in phosphate buffer saline solution) was added to microplates and incubated for 3 h at 37 °C. After 2 h, lysis buffer (20% SDS, 50% dimethyl formamide) was added to each well and then incubated overnight at 37 °C for solubilization of formazan crystals. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm with the aid of a 96-well multi-scanner auto reader (Biotek, Winooski, Vermont) with the lysis buffer serving as blank¹⁶. The percentage inhibition was calculated using the following formula :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 - (T - T_0 / C - T_0) \times 100$$

where, T = optical density of the cells before treating with sample, T_0 = optical density of the sample and C = optical density of the control.

Flow cytometric analysis of apoptotic cell death by quantitation of caspase-3 :

The HeLa cell lines were treated with briefly 10 µg of the extracts for 12 h and then harvested, washed with phosphate buffer saline and incubated with caspase-3. The activity of caspase-3 was measured using the active caspase-3 apoptosis kit (BD Pharmingen, USA) following the method explained earlier¹⁷.

GC-MS analysis of bioactive extract and identification of components :

The GC-MS analysis of methanolic extract of *D. sepiaria* leaves were performed using Clarus 680 Perkin-Elmer gas chromatography equipped with an Elite-5 MS capillary column (30.0 m, 0.25 mm ID, 250 µm df) and clarus 600 Perkin-Elmer mass detector. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 ml/min and the injector was operated at 250 °C and the oven temperature was programmed as follows; initial temp. 60 °C for 2 min, ramp 10 °C/min to 300 °C, hold 4 min, for a run time of 30 m. Interpretation of mass spectrum of GC-MS was done using the database of NIST, WILEY8. The mass spectrum of the unknown component was compared with the spectrum of the known components stored in the library. The name, molecular weight and structure of the components of the test materials were ascertained.

Results and discussion

In the present study, attempts were made to estimate the various medicinally active constituents present in *D. sepiaria* leaf extract qualitatively. The saponins, anthraquinones, alkaloids, steroids constituents were present in petroleum ether extracts. The flavonoids, terpenoids and carbohydrates in the methanol extract. Among the tested phyto constituents the tannins and amino acid were absent in both the fractions.

The toxicity is measured by the MTT dye uptaking method where active cells convert the water soluble MTT to an insoluble purple formazan, further solubilized and its concentration was determined by optical density⁷. When cervical cancer cells, HeLa were treated with different concentrations of methanolic leaf extracts of *D. sepiaria*, it showed a dose dependent cytotoxic effect. As the concentration increases from 0.01 to 100 µg/ml the percentage inhibition increases from 16.29% to 80.56% of the control respectively with an IC₅₀ value of 10 µg/ml. The structural changes were observed under inverted microscope and were seen to have detached from the plate. More number of dead cells was observed as the concentration increases. These results reveal that the morphological changes may due to apoptosis. It has been reported that cells undergoing apoptosis exhibit cytoplas-

mic blebbing, nuclear shrinkage, chromatin condensation, irregularity in shape⁸. We found that there is a drastic decrease in the viability of HeLa cells at higher concentration 100 g/ml (Fig. 1).

our literature reports this is the first scientific research on the cytotoxic activities of *D. sepiaria*.

The crude extract was further identified by GC-MS analysis which led to the identification of a number of

Fig 1. (A) Effect of methanolic leaf extract of *D. sepiaria* on HeLa cell lines. (B) Quantification of caspase-3 for control cells. (C) Quantification of caspase-3 for extract treated cells.

The MTT assay is a very effective method to evaluate the cytotoxic activity, but by this method we could not able to differentiate between cells dying from apoptosis or necrosis. The caspases are known to form integral parts of apoptotic pathway, especially caspase-3, when activated, has many cellular targets that, when severed and/or activated, produces the morphologic features of apoptosis⁹. To provide further evidence supporting the involvement of apoptosis, the caspase-3 was quantified by flow cytometry. Treatment of HeLa cell lines with methanolic extract of *D. sepiaria* at a concentration 10 µg/ml, for 12 h resulted in the expression of caspase-3 and increase in the caspase-3 enzyme activity was observed. The results showed a significant increase of caspase-3 levels after treatment of test extracts (Fig. 1). The result proves that the cytotoxic cell death is due to apoptosis. After treatment of the sample it showed a 60% increase in the caspase-3 cells from 0.24%. The cytotoxicity of methanolic extract of *D. sepiaria* may be due to the presence of flavonoids and phenolic groups in the extracts. The flavonoids have reported for their cytotoxic activity due to the presence of phenolic groups¹⁰. As per

compounds. The spectrum profile of GC-MS confirmed the presence of 10 major components (Table 1).

The benzofuran complexes¹¹ and 2-methoxy-4-vinyl phenol are reported to have anti-inflammatory, analgesic

Table 1. Compounds identified in the crude extracts of *D. sepiaria* by GC-MS

Sr. no.	RT	Name of the compound	Molecular formula	Mol. wt
1.	5.46	Clofexamide	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	284
2.	9.48	3-Methyl, benzaldehyde	C ₈ H ₈ O	120
3.	14.88	Myo-inositol	C ₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	194
4.	16.11	2-Propenoic acid, 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-, methyl ester	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₃	178
5.	17.00	Oleyl alcohol	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O	268
6.	17.05	4-Methoxy-6-methyl-6,7-dihydro-4H-	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₃	168
7.	17.88	Furan	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270
8.	17.96	Tetra decanoic acid	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₃	292
9.	19.56	Benzene propanoic acid	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂	138
10.	19.67	3-Methyl-2-(2-oxopropyl) furan phytol	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	296

and anticancer properties¹². The Myo-inositol was well reported as anti-diabetic compound¹³ and also possess moderate anticancer activity where as the best anticancer results were obtained from the combination of inositol hexaphosphate (IP6) plus inositol¹⁴.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of the present work shows that the methanolic extract of *D. sepiaria* showed excellent cytotoxicity by the activation of apoptosis pathway against HeLa cell lines. Additionally the bioactive molecules which may be responsible for the toxicity was identified by GC-MS analysis. Based on the initial screening work reported here, further studies aimed to identify the active compounds of *D. sepiaria* leaf extract and the elucidation of their mechanism as cancer therapeutics are narrated.

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